

BIOSYNTHESIS OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES FROM *TRICHODERMA SPECIES* ISOLATED FROM AGRICULTURAL SOIL

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Introduction. The increasing need for environmentally friendly and sustainable technologies has led to a notable interest in the synthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNP) by biological techniques [1]. *Trichoderma species*, a kind of fungi widely used in agriculture due to their ability to act as biocontrol agents, present a viable method for AgNP production [2]. By producing secondary metabolites that may reduce silver ions (Ag⁺) to silver nanoparticles, these fungi offer a safer alternative to chemical manufacturing techniques without harming the environment [3]. The main objective of this study is to synthesize silver nanoparticle (AgNPs) from *Trichoderma species* isolated from the agricultural soil.

Methodology: The *Trichoderma* fungal cultures were isolated from soil collected from the agricultural land of Prayagraj, India. Isolated strains were further incubated with silver nitrate (AgNO₃) under different conditions in order to carry out the biosynthesis of AgNPs [4]. To attain optimal production and stability of AgNPs, critical parameters including pH, temperature, concentration of silver ions, and duration of incubation were tuned [5]. To ascertain the size, shape, and crystalline structure of the nanoparticles, characterization procedures included X-ray diffraction (XRD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and UV-Vis spectroscopy [6].

Results and Discussion: In this study, out of ten *Trichoderma* strains isolated from soil samples, *T. asperellum*, *T. viride*, and *T. harzianum* were identified as potent candidates for the extracellular synthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs).

Figure1: Biosynthesis of Silver Nanoparticles from isolated *Trichoderma* sp.

The successful synthesis was indicated by the characteristic brown color and confirmed by UV-vis spectroscopy, which showed maximum absorption between 410 nm and 450 nm. TEM analysis revealed monodispersed, spherical nanoparticles with sizes of 20 nm, 38 nm, and 59 nm for *T. asperellum*, *T. viride*, and *T. harzianum*, respectively. The uniform size distribution and

crystalline nature of the AgNPs were further validated by TEM and XRD analyses. These findings demonstrate the potential of these *Trichoderma* strains in the green synthesis of AgNPs.

Figure 2: UV-visible spectrum and TEM analysis of synthesized silver nanoparticles from isolated *Trichoderma* sp.

Conclusion: This research highlights the effectiveness of *Trichoderma* species in the green synthesis of AgNP, presenting a sustainable alternative to traditional chemical methods. The study also underscores the potential of these biogenically synthesized nanoparticles in combating microbial pathogens, with implications for their use in various industries. Further research will focus on scaling up the synthesis process and exploring additional applications.

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